

A STUDY OF SECURITY MECHANISMS IMPLEMENTED IN NETWORK PROTOCOLS

Ram Krishna Akuli¹, J. Durga Prasad Rao² and Satyendra Kurariya³

¹Scholar CVRU, Bilaspur.

²Additional Director and HOD Computer Science, Shri Shankaracharya Mahavidyalaya, Bhilai

³HOD Computer Science, Mata Gujari College, Jabalpur.

Ram Krishna Akuli

ABSTRACT

In this paper we are describing some widely used mechanisms used by various network protocols for providing security. When these protocols were designed it was considered that there is no existence of intruders, and every device in the network can be trusted by others. But in present scenario this

assumption fails. The network situation has completely changed in last several years and so we must consider that some properties of protocols in existence might be getting abused or misused. Some of the issues about designing the basic rules and requirements for secure network protocols are also described.

KEYWORDS :Network Protocols , Security Mechanisms , properties of protocols .

INTRODUCTION :

This paper describes some security restrictions and the mechanism used in networking protocols. It is essential to know that people started to worry about network security much later than networks were involved. Until now, there was no security [1]. Other issues like slow

network connections, extreme number of faults on physical links, etc. were being taken care of. Complicated protocols were not used and simple protocols were relied upon. For instance, key exchange protocols are still not implemented in all the systems. The protocols used until now, should now become obsolete. The applications designed to work with these, unsecured protocols, are not rewritten to secure versions because of compatibility requirements or costs.

BAD SECURITY

Mostly users are not aware of low level, unsecured protocols [2]. Security mechanism in low

layers of the OSI model is not very important. One of the network attacks is sniffing. Ethernet sends network 'frames' to each device connected in the network. The destination device checks destination address before accepting or ignoring the received frame. In this method, all the data can be easily sniffed. Every switch and bridge used for performance requirements checks source addresses in network frames and attaches it to its physical interface, protecting the network against sniffing attacks. The data is sent to a specific device, not all.

Another method is called spoofing. There is no authentication method used, and any device can lie and change source address in. This flaw is well known and used with ARP poisoning. It is difficult to connect a certain request with a certain response. Only one host should reply for one request. Intruder may respond with ARP replies without receiving the ARP requests. This leads to problems with ARP cache, it is poisoned. Now onwards the victim sends all the data to the intruder instead of correct destination.

II.METHODOLOGY

TCP model protocols are the most famous in computer networks [3]. But, there is no build-in security mechanism implemented. TCP header contains sequence and acknowledgement numbers. The sequence number is an offset to byte 1 of TCP packet, so it is increased in next packet by the value of total length of current packet. However, if SYN flag is also set, sequence number is byte 1 in the current TCP session. Usually, initial sequence number is set to 1. Acknowledgement number is used with ACK flag; it shows that the packet is received. This leads to TCP/IP hijacking. If an intruder listens and receives whole packets it can easily predict next sequence and acknowledgement numbers. There are at least three consequences of such attacks:

- 1) Infected packet will be accepted and processed by a victim.
- 2) The real sender will send TCP/IP packets with wrong numbers without incrementing sequence number.
- 3) ACK packets, sent by a victim will be ignored because of wrong acknowledgement numbers.
- 4) RST injecting is a very simple form of injecting TCP/IP. If the acknowledgment number is correct but the source is spoofed, the receiver will accept injected RST packet and reset the connection.

PREVENTION METHODS-

- 1) Use initial sequence numbers (ISN), different than 1[4]. The value of this 32-bit counter should be increased by a value of one after every 4 microseconds.
- 2) Another method is to use randomly generated initial sequence numbers. It makes predicting sequence number harder. A real sender can detect TCP/IP hijacking.
- 3) The only way to prevent against RST attacks is to block spoofed packet which in turn also blocks the TCP/IP hijacking.

III.CONCLUSION

There is no formal guideline for creating secure protocols. Vulnerabilities and threats on security are clear. Protocols used locally are not secure. Therefore we see the necessity of segregating all these issues and analyze them. Creation of own protected protocols should be encouraged. Current protocols do not provide integrity or confidentiality. Security is an obligation today and no more an option.

IV. REFERENCES

- [1]P. C. van Orschot, S. A. Vanstone and A. J. Menezes, Handbook of Applied Cryptography, CRC (1996)
- [2]J. Erickson, Hacking – The Art of Exploitation, San Francisco (2003).
- [3]D. LeBlanc, J. Viega, M. Howard .The 19 Deadly Sins of Software Security, McGraw-Hill/Osborne, California (2005).
- [4]Auer, S., Bizer, C., Kobilarov, G., Lehmann, J., Cyganiak, R., & Ives, Z. (2007). Dbpedia: A nucleus for a web of open data (pp. 722-735). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [5]Kepner, J., & Gilbert, J. (Eds.). (2011). Graph algorithms in the language of linear algebra (Vol. 22). SIAM.
- [6]Stewart, J. M., Chapple, M., & Gibson, D. (2012). CISSP: Certified Information Systems Security Professional Study Guide. John Wiley & Sons.
- [7]Gampala, V., Inuganti, S., & Muppidi, S. (2012). Data security in cloud computing with elliptic curve cryptography. International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering (IJSCE), 2(3), 138-141.
- [8]Eckel, B. (2013). Thinking in Java 3rd edition.
- [9]Harris, S., Harper, A., Ness, J., Williams, T., & Lenkey, G. (2011). Gray Hat Hacking
- [10]A.S. Tanenbaum, Computer Networks, New Jersey (2003).